

Monologhi per clarinetto

Op. 11

Diego Casadei

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Capriccio 1

Diego Casadei

The musical score for "Capriccio 1" by Diego Casadei is written in 4/4 time. It consists of eight staves of music. The first staff begins with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The music features a variety of rhythmic patterns, including eighth and sixteenth notes, often grouped with slurs and accents. The second staff starts at measure 6 and includes a triplet of eighth notes. The third staff starts at measure 9 and continues with similar rhythmic motifs. The fourth staff starts at measure 11 and shows a change in the melodic line. The fifth staff starts at measure 15 and features more complex rhythmic figures. The sixth staff starts at measure 19 and contains several triplet markings over eighth notes. The seventh staff starts at measure 23 and continues the melodic development. The eighth staff starts at measure 28 and concludes with a triplet of eighth notes. The piece ends with a final cadence.

Capriccio 1

32

Musical staff 32-33: Treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#). The staff contains a continuous eighth-note melody with various slurs and ties.

34

Musical staff 34-35: Treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#). The staff contains a continuous eighth-note melody with various slurs and ties.

38

Musical staff 38-39: Treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#). The staff contains a continuous eighth-note melody with various slurs and ties. Trills are marked with a '3' above the notes.

42

Musical staff 42-43: Treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#). The staff contains a continuous eighth-note melody with various slurs and ties. Trills are marked with a '3' above the notes. Fingerings 7, 9, and 6 are indicated below the staff.

44

Musical staff 44-45: Treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#). The staff contains a continuous eighth-note melody with various slurs and ties. Trills are marked with a '3' above the notes. A fingering of 6 is indicated below the staff.

48

Musical staff 48-49: Treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#). The staff contains a continuous eighth-note melody with various slurs and ties.

52

Musical staff 52-53: Treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#). The staff contains a continuous eighth-note melody with various slurs and ties. The piece concludes with a diamond-shaped symbol.

Fantasia on "The Flight of the Bumble Bee"

Presto

Diego Casadei (1995)

3

6

8

10

12

15

18

21

24

26

28

31

Popeye

Diego Casadei

The musical score for 'Popeye' is written in a single system with ten staves. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 2/4. The music is characterized by a rhythmic melody with many eighth and sixteenth notes, often grouped in pairs or fours. The melody starts on a G4 note and moves generally upwards, with some chromatic descents. The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, ties, and dynamic markings. The piece concludes with a final cadence on a G4 note.

Solfeggetto

29.4.2020

Diego Casadei (after C. Ph. E. Bach)

1

4

7

10

13

16

20

23

26

29

Präludium BWV 999 in C moll

Johann Sebastian Bach
(adapted by Diego Casadei)

Clarinet in B $\flat$

The image displays a musical score for Clarinet in B $\flat$, consisting of seven staves of music. The score is written in treble clef with a key signature of one flat (B $\flat$) and a time signature of 3/4. The music features a continuous eighth-note pattern with various melodic and harmonic developments. Measure numbers 4, 7, 10, 13, 16, and 19 are indicated at the beginning of their respective staves. The notation includes slurs, ties, and accidentals (sharps and naturals) to indicate specific notes and phrasing.

Musical score for Präludium BWV 999 in C minor, measures 22-43. The score is written in treble clef with a key signature of one flat (B-flat) and a common time signature. The music features a complex rhythmic pattern with many beamed eighth and sixteenth notes, often grouped in pairs or groups of four. Slurs are used to indicate phrasing across several measures. The piece concludes with a final measure (43) marked with a double bar line.

Measures 22, 25, 28, 31, 34, 37, 40, and 43 are indicated by measure numbers at the beginning of their respective staves. The word *rit.* (ritardando) is written below the staff at the end of measure 40.

Tocatta in re minore

Parafrasi da Domenico Scarlatti, K 141 L 422 Diego Casadei

Allegro

Clarinet

7

15

25

33

41

49

57

64

71

Toccata in re minore

78

86

94

102

110

118

127

135

143

151

Paganini - Capriccio no. 1

D. Casadei
(2006-03-08)

Play everything soft-staccato or 2 legato + 2 staccato.

Andante

The image displays the first 16 measures of Paganini's Capriccio no. 1. The score is written for a single melodic line on a treble clef staff. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#), and the time signature is 2/4. The tempo is marked 'Andante'. The piece begins with a quarter rest, followed by a series of eighth-note patterns. Measures 1-4 feature a sequence of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F#4, E4, D4, C4, B3, A3, G3, F#3, E3, D3, C3, B2, A2, G2, F#2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1, F#1, E1, D1, C1, B0, A0, G0, F#0, E0, D0, C0, B-1, A-1, G-1, F#-1, E-1, D-1, C-1, B-2, A-2, G-2, F#-2, E-2, D-2, C-2, B-3, A-3, G-3, F#-3, E-3, D-3, C-3, B-4, A-4, G-4, F#-4, E-4, D-4, C-4, B-5, A-5, G-5, F#-5, E-5, D-5, C-5, B-6, A-6, G-6, F#-6, E-6, D-6, C-6, B-7, A-7, G-7, F#-7, E-7, D-7, C-7, B-8, A-8, G-8, F#-8, E-8, D-8, C-8, B-9, A-9, G-9, F#-9, E-9, D-9, C-9, B-10, A-10, G-10, F#-10, E-10, D-10, C-10, B-11, A-11, G-11, F#-11, E-11, D-11, C-11, B-12, A-12, G-12, F#-12, E-12, D-12, C-12, B-13, A-13, G-13, F#-13, E-13, D-13, C-13, B-14, A-14, G-14, F#-14, E-14, D-14, C-14, B-15, A-15, G-15, F#-15, E-15, D-15, C-15, B-16, A-16, G-16, F#-16, E-16, D-16, C-16, B-17, A-17, G-17, F#-17, E-17, D-17, C-17, B-18, A-18, G-18, F#-18, E-18, D-18, C-18, B-19, A-19, G-19, F#-19, E-19, D-19, C-19, B-20, A-20, G-20, F#-20, E-20, D-20, C-20, B-21, A-21, G-21, F#-21, E-21, D-21, C-21, B-22, A-22, G-22, F#-22, E-22, D-22, C-22, B-23, A-23, G-23, F#-23, E-23, D-23, C-23, B-24, A-24, G-24, F#-24, E-24, D-24, C-24, B-25, A-25, G-25, F#-25, E-25, D-25, C-25, B-26, A-26, G-26, F#-26, E-26, D-26, C-26, B-27, A-27, G-27, F#-27, E-27, D-27, C-27, B-28, A-28, G-28, F#-28, E-28, D-28, C-28, B-29, A-29, G-29, F#-29, E-29, D-29, C-29, B-30, A-30, G-30, F#-30, E-30, D-30, C-30, B-31, A-31, G-31, F#-31, E-31, D-31, C-31, B-32, A-32, G-32, F#-32, E-32, D-32, C-32, B-33, A-33, G-33, F#-33, E-33, D-33, C-33, B-34, A-34, G-34, F#-34, E-34, D-34, C-34, B-35, A-35, G-35, F#-35, E-35, D-35, C-35, B-36, A-36, G-36, F#-36, E-36, D-36, C-36, B-37, A-37, G-37, F#-37, E-37, D-37, C-37, B-38, A-38, G-38, F#-38, E-38, D-38, C-38, B-39, A-39, G-39, F#-39, E-39, D-39, C-39, B-40, A-40, G-40, F#-40, E-40, D-40, C-40, B-41, A-41, G-41, F#-41, E-41, D-41, C-41, B-42, A-42, G-42, F#-42, E-42, D-42, C-42, B-43, A-43, G-43, F#-43, E-43, D-43, C-43, B-44, A-44, G-44, F#-44, E-44, D-44, C-44, B-45, A-45, G-45, F#-45, E-45, D-45, C-45, B-46, A-46, G-46, F#-46, E-46, D-46, C-46, B-47, A-47, G-47, F#-47, E-47, D-47, C-47, B-48, A-48, G-48, F#-48, E-48, D-48, C-48, B-49, A-49, G-49, F#-49, E-49, D-49, C-49, B-50, A-50, G-50, F#-50, E-50, D-50, C-50, B-51, A-51, G-51, F#-51, E-51, D-51, C-51, B-52, A-52, G-52, F#-52, E-52, D-52, C-52, B-53, A-53, G-53, F#-53, E-53, D-53, C-53, B-54, A-54, G-54, F#-54, E-54, D-54, C-54, B-55, A-55, G-55, F#-55, E-55, D-55, C-55, B-56, A-56, G-56, F#-56, E-56, D-56, C-56, B-57, A-57, G-57, F#-57, E-57, D-57, C-57, B-58, A-58, G-58, F#-58, E-58, D-58, C-58, B-59, A-59, G-59, F#-59, E-59, D-59, C-59, B-60, A-60, G-60, F#-60, E-60, D-60, C-60, B-61, A-61, G-61, F#-61, E-61, D-61, C-61, B-62, A-62, G-62, F#-62, E-62, D-62, C-62, B-63, A-63, G-63, F#-63, E-63, D-63, C-63, B-64, A-64, G-64, F#-64, E-64, D-64, C-64, B-65, A-65, G-65, F#-65, E-65, D-65, C-65, B-66, A-66, G-66, F#-66, E-66, D-66, C-66, B-67, A-67, G-67, F#-67, E-67, D-67, C-67, B-68, A-68, G-68, F#-68, E-68, D-68, C-68, B-69, A-69, G-69, F#-69, E-69, D-69, C-69, B-70, A-70, G-70, F#-70, E-70, D-70, C-70, B-71, A-71, G-71, F#-71, E-71, D-71, C-71, B-72, A-72, G-72, F#-72, E-72, D-72, C-72, B-73, A-73, G-73, F#-73, E-73, D-73, C-73, B-74, A-74, G-74, F#-74, E-74, D-74, C-74, B-75, A-75, G-75, F#-75, E-75, D-75, C-75, B-76, A-76, G-76, F#-76, E-76, D-76, C-76, B-77, A-77, G-77, F#-77, E-77, D-77, C-77, B-78, A-78, G-78, F#-78, E-78, D-78, C-78, B-79, A-79, G-79, F#-79, E-79, D-79, C-79, B-80, A-80, G-80, F#-80, E-80, D-80, C-80, B-81, A-81, G-81, F#-81, E-81, D-81, C-81, B-82, A-82, G-82, F#-82, E-82, D-82, C-82, B-83, A-83, G-83, F#-83, E-83, D-83, C-83, B-84, A-84, G-84, F#-84, E-84, D-84, C-84, B-85, A-85, G-85, F#-85, E-85, D-85, C-85, B-86, A-86, G-86, F#-86, E-86, D-86, C-86, B-87, A-87, G-87, F#-87, E-87, D-87, C-87, B-88, A-88, G-88, F#-88, E-88, D-88, C-88, B-89, A-89, G-89, F#-89, E-89, D-89, C-89, B-90, A-90, G-90, F#-90, 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C-151, B-152, A-152, G-152, F#-152, E-152, D-152, C-152, B-153, A-153, G-153, F#-153, E-153, D-153, C-153, B-154, A-154, G-154, F#-154, E-154, D-154, C-154, B-155, A-155, G-155, F#-155, E-155, D-155, C-155, B-156, A-156, G-156, F#-156, E-156, D-156, C-156, B-157, A-157, G-157, F#-157, E-157, D-157, C-157, B-158, A-158, G-158, F#-158, E-158, D-158, C-158, B-159, A-159, G-159, F#-159, E-159, D-159, C-159, B-160, A-160, G-160, F#-160, E-160, D-160, C-160, B-161, A-161, G-161, F#-161, E-161, D-161, C-161, B-162, A-162, G-162, F#-162, E-162, D-162, C-162, B-163, A-163, G-163, F#-163, E-163, D-163, C-163, B-164, A-164, G-164, F#-164, E-164, D-164, C-164, B-165, A-165, G-165, F#-165, E-165, D-165, C-165, B-166, A-166, G-166, F#-166, E-166, D-166, C-166, B-167, A-167, G-167, F#-167, E-167, D-167, C-167, B-168, A-168, G-168, F#-168, E-168, D-168, C-168, B-169, A-169, G-169, F#-169, E-169, D-169, C-169, B-170, A-170, G-170, F#-170, E-170, D-170, C-170, B-171, A-171, G-171, F#-171, E-171, D-171, C-171, B-172, A-172, G-172, F#-172, E-172, D-172, C-172, B-173, A-173, G-173, F#-173, E-173, D-173, C-173, B-174, A-174, G-174, F#-174, E-174, D-174, C-174, B-175, A-175, G-175, F#-175, E-175, D-175, C-175, B-176, A-176, G-176, F#-176, E-176, D-176, C-176, B-177, A-177, G-177, F#-177, E-177, D-177, C-177, B-178, A-178, G-178, F#-178, E-178, D-178, C-178, B-179, A-179, G-179, F#-179, E-179, D-179, C-179, B-180, A-180, G-180, F#-180, E-180, D-180, C-180, B-181, A-181, G-181, F#-181, E-181, D-181, C-181, B-182, A-182, G-182, F#-182, E-182, D-182, C-182, B-183, A-183, G-183, F#-183, E-183, D-183, C-183, B-184, A-184, G-184, F#-184, E-184, D-184, C-184, B-185, A-185, G-185, F#-185, E-185, D-185, C-185, B-186, A-186, G-186, F#-186, E-186, D-186, C-186, B-187, A-187, G-187, F#-187, E-187, D-187, C-187, B-188, A-188, G-188, F#-188, E-188, D-188, C-188, B-189, A-189, G-189, F#-189, E-189, D-189, C-189, B-190, A-190, G-190, F#-190, E-190, D-190, C-190, B-191, A-191, G-191, F#-191, E-191, D-191, C-191, B-192, A-192, G-192, F#-192, E-192, D-192, C-192, B-193, A-193, G-193, F#-193, E-193, D-193, C-193, B-194, A-194, G-194, F#-194, E-194, D-194, C-194, B-195, A-195, G-195, F#-195, E-195, D-195, C-195, B-196, A-196, G-196, F#-196, E-196, D-196, C-196, B-197, A-197, G-197, F#-197, E-197, D-197, C-197, B-198, A-198, G-198, F#-198, E-198, D-198, C-198, B-199, A-199, G-199, F#-199, E-199, D-199, C-199, B-200, A-200, G-200, F#-200, E-200, D-200, C-200, B-201, A-201, G-201, F#-201, E-201, D-201, C-201, B-202, A-202, G-202, F#-202, E-202, D-202, C-202, B-203, A-203, G-203, F#-203, E-203, D-203, C-203, B-204, A-204, G-204, F#-204, E-204, D-204, C-204, B-205, A-205, G-205, F#-205, E-205, D-205, C-205, B-206, A-206, G-206, F#-206, E-206, D-206, C-206, B-207, A-207, G-207, F#-207, E-207, D-207, C-207, B-208, A-208, G-208, F#-208, E-208, D-208, C-208, B-209, A-209, G-209, F#-209, E-209, D-209, C-209, B-210, A-210, G-210, F#-210, E-210, D-210, C-210, B-211, A-211, G-211, F#-211, E-211, D-211, C-211, B-212, A-212, G-212, F#-212, E-212, D-212, C-212, B-213, A-213, G-213, F#-213, E-213, D-213, C-213, B-214, A-214, G-214, F#-214, E-214, D-214, C-214, B-215, A-215, G-215, F#-215, E-215, D-215, C-215, B-216, A-216, G-216, F#-216, E-216, D-216, C-216, B-217, A-217, G-217, F#-217, E-217, D-217, C-217, B-218, A-218, G-218, F#-218, E-218, D-218, C-218, B-219, A-219, G-219, F#-219, E-219, D-219, C-219, B-220, A-220, G-220, F#-220, E-220, D-220, C-220, B-221, A-221, G-221, F#-221, E-221, D-221, C-221, B-222, A-222, G-222, F#-222, E-222, D-222, C-222, B-223, A-223, G-223, F#-223, E-223, D-223, C-223, B-224, A-224, G-224, F#-224, E-224, D-224, C-224, B-225, A-225, G-225, F#-225, E-225, D-225, C-225, B-226, A-226, G-226, F#-226, E-226, D-226, C-226, B-227, A-227, G-227, F#-227, E-227, D-227, C-227, B-228, A-228, G-228, F#-228, E-228, D-228, C-228, B-229, A-229, G-229, F#-229, E-229, D-229, C-229, B-230, A-230, G-230, F#-230, E-230, D-230, C-230, B-231, A-231, G-231, F#-231, E-231, D-231, C-231, B-232, A-232, G-232, F#-232, E-232, D-232, C-232, B-233, A-233, G-233, F#-233, E-233, D-233, C-233, B-234, A-234, G-234, F#-234, E-234, D-234, C-234, B-235, A-235, G-235, F#-235, E-235, D-235, C-235, B-236, A-236, G-236, F#-236, E-236, D-236, C-236, B-237, A-237, G-237, F#-237, E-237, D-237, C-237, B-238, A-238, G-238, F#-238, E-238, D-238, C-238, B-239, A-239, G-239, F#-239, E-239, D-239, C-239, B-240, A-240, G-240, F#-240, E-240, D-240, C-240, B-241, A-241, G-241, F#-241, E-241, D-241, C-241, B-242, A-242, G-242, F#-242, E-242, D-242, C-242, B-243, A-243, G-243, F#-243, E-243, D-243, C-243, B-244, A-244, G-244, F#-244, E-244, D-244, C-244, B-245, A-245, G-245, F#-245, E-245, D-245, C-245, B-246, A-246, G-246, F#-246, E-246, D-246, C-246, B-247, A-247, G-247, F#-247, E-247, D-247, C-247, B-248, A-248, G-248, F#-248, E-248, D-248, C-248, B-249, A-249, G-249, F#-249, E-249, D-249, C-249, B-250, A-250, G-250, F#-250, E-250, D-250, C-250, B-251, A-251, G-251, F#-251, E-251, D-251, C-251, B-252, A-252, G-252, F#-252, E-252, D-252, C-252, B-253, A-253, G-253, F#-253, E-253, D-253, C-253, B-254, A-254, G-254, F#-254, E-254, D-254, C-254, B-255, A-255, G-255, F#-255, E-255, D-255, C-255, B-256, A-256, G-256, F#-256, E-256, D-256, C-256, B-257, A-257, G-257, F#-257, E-257, D-257, C-257, B-258, A-258, G-258, F#-258, E-258, D-258, C-258, B-259, A-259, G-259, F#-259, E-259, D-259, C-259, B-260, A-260, G-260, F#-260, E-260, D-260, C-260, B-261, A-261, G-261, F#-261, E-261, D-261, C-261, B-262, A-262, G-262, F#-262, E-262, D-262, C-262, B-263, A-263, G-263, F#-263, E-263, D-263, C-263, B-264, A-264, G-264, F#-264, E-264, D-264, C-264, B-265, A-265, G-265, F#-265, E-265, D-265, C-265, B-266, A-266, G-266, F#-266, E-266, D-266, C-266, B-267, A-267, G-267, F#-267, E-267, D-267, C-267, B-268, A-268, G-268, F#-268, E-268, D-268, C-268, B-269, A-269, G-269, F#-269, E-269, D-269, C-269, B-270, A-270, G-270, F#-270, E-270, D-270, C-270, B-271, A-271, G-271, F#-271, E-271, D-271, C-271, B-272, A-272, G-272, F#-272, E-272, D-272, C-272, B-273, A-273, G-273, F#-273, E-273, D-273, C-273, B-274, A-274, G-274, F#-274, E-274, D-274, C-274, B-275, A-275, G-275, F#-275, E-275, D-275, C-275, B-276, A-276, G-276, F#-276, E-276, D-276, C-276, B-277, A-277, G-277, F#-277, E-277, D-277, C-277, B-278, A-278, G-278, F#-278, E-278, D-278, C-278, B-279, A-279, G-279, F#-279, E-279, D-279, C-279, B-280, A-280, G-280, F#-280, E-280, D-280, C-280, B-281, A-281, G-281, F#-281, E-281, D-281, C-281, B-282, A-282, G-282, F#-282, E-282, D-282, C-282, B-283, A-283, G-283, F#-283, E-283, D-283, C-283, B-284, A-284, G-284, F#-284, E-284, D-284, C-284, B-285, A-285, G-285, F#-285, E-285, D-285, C-285, B-286, A-286, G-286, F#-286, E-286, D-286, C-286, B-287, A-287, G-287, F#-287, E-287, D-287, C-287, B-288, A-288, G-288, F#-288, E-288, D-288, C-288, B-289, A-289, G-289, F#-289, E-289, D-289, C-289, B-290, A-290, G-290, F#-290, E-290, D-290, C-290, B-291, A-291, G-291, F#-291, E-291, D-291, C-291, B-292, A-292, G-292, F#-292, E-292, D-292, C-292, B-293, A-293, G-293, F#-293, E-293, D-293, C-293, B-294, A-294, G-294, F#-294, E-294, D-294, C-294, B-295, A-295, G-295, F#-295, E-295, D-295, C-295, B-296, A-296, G-296, F#

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61

64

67

70

73

76

Paganini - Capriccio no. 12

D. Casadei
(2004-01-23)

Allegro

The image displays the first thirteen measures of Paganini's Capriccio no. 12. The music is written on a single staff in G major (one sharp) and common time (C). The tempo is marked 'Allegro'. The score consists of seven lines of music, each starting with a measure number (1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13). The notation includes eighth and sixteenth notes, often beamed together in groups, and rests. The key signature is G major, and the time signature is common time. The music is characterized by its rapid, rhythmic patterns and frequent use of accidentals.

15

17

19

21

24

26

28

30

32

Musical staff 32-33: Treble clef, key signature of one flat (B-flat). The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

34

Musical staff 34-35: Treble clef, key signature of one flat. The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

36

Musical staff 36-37: Treble clef, key signature of one flat. The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

38

Musical staff 38-39: Treble clef, key signature of one flat. The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

40

Musical staff 40-41: Treble clef, key signature of one flat. The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

42

Musical staff 42-43: Treble clef, key signature of one flat. The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

44

Musical staff 44-45: Treble clef, key signature of one flat. The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

46

Musical staff 46-47: Treble clef, key signature of one flat. The staff contains two measures of music. The first measure starts with a B-flat and contains a series of eighth notes: B-flat, A, G, F, E, D, C, B-flat. The second measure starts with a B and contains a series of eighth notes: B, A, G, F, E, D, C, B.

48

50

52

54

56

58

60

62

64

Paganini - Capriccio 24

Diego Casadei

41

49

53

57

62

67

73

79

This image shows a page of musical notation for Paganini's Capriccio 24, measures 41 through 83. The score is written in a single system on a grand staff (treble clef). The music is in 24/16 time and features a variety of rhythmic patterns, including eighth and sixteenth notes, and rests. The key signature is one sharp (F#). The notation includes many slurs, ties, and dynamic markings. The measures are numbered 41, 49, 53, 57, 62, 67, 73, and 79. The piece concludes with a double bar line and repeat dots at the end of measure 83.

Paganini - Capriccio 24

85

Musical staff 85-90: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 85-90 feature a sequence of triplets of eighth notes, with some measures containing slurs and accidentals (sharps and naturals).

90

Musical staff 90-95: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 90-95 continue the triplet eighth-note pattern, including a measure with a natural sign and a measure with a sharp sign.

95

Musical staff 95-99: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 95-99 show the triplet eighth-note pattern, with a double bar line and repeat sign at the end of measure 98.

99

Musical staff 99-103: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 99-103 continue the triplet eighth-note pattern, with a double bar line and repeat sign at the end of measure 102.

103

Musical staff 103-107: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 103-107 feature a sequence of eighth notes, with some measures containing slurs and accidentals (sharps and naturals).

107

Musical staff 107-111: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 107-111 continue the eighth-note sequence, including a measure with a sharp sign and a measure with a natural sign.

111

Musical staff 111-117: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 111-117 continue the eighth-note sequence, with a double bar line and repeat sign at the end of measure 116.

117

Musical staff 117-121: Treble clef, 2/4 time signature. Measures 117-121 continue the eighth-note sequence, with a double bar line and repeat sign at the end of measure 120.

123

129

134

138

142

146

149

151

This page of musical notation for Paganini's Capriccio 24 contains eight staves of music, numbered 123 through 151. The notation is in treble clef and features a variety of rhythmic and melodic patterns. Measures 123-128 show a melodic line with slurs and a repeat sign. Measures 129-133 continue the melodic development. Measures 134-137 feature a wide intervallic leap. Measures 138-141 are characterized by triplets and slurs. Measures 142-145 show a sequence of triplets. Measures 146-148 include slurs and triplets. Measures 149-150 consist of long, sweeping slurs over a series of notes. Measure 151 concludes the section with a final melodic phrase and a repeat sign.

Studio corale

Clarinetto in Si b. Cantare la seconda voce.
Bb clarinet. Sing the second voice.

Diego Casadei

The musical score is written for a B-flat Clarinet in 4/4 time, B-flat major. It consists of 28 measures. The dynamics are marked as follows: *mp* (measures 1-4), *f* (measures 5-6), *p* (measures 7-10), *mf* (measures 11-16), *f* (measures 17-19), and *p* (measures 20-28). The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, accents, and trills.

29 *f* *p*

31 *mf*

34 *dim.*

38

43 *mp* *cresc.*

46 *dim.* *p*

51

57 *dim.*

2017: first idea

2019-08-28: piece almost complete

2021-01-01: revision + Duo corale

2023-07-11: small improvements

Prélude après Rachmaninov

Diego Casadei

2023-07-01

Lento $\text{♩} = 54$

Clarinet in A

3 *mf*

3 *p*

4 *cresc.* *dim.*

5 *cresc.*

6 *mp*

7

8 *cresc.*

9 *cresc.*

©2023

10 *p*

Musical notation for measures 10-11. Measure 10 starts with a piano (*p*) dynamic. It features a triplet of eighth notes in the right hand and a triplet of eighth notes in the left hand. Measure 11 continues with similar triplet patterns.

11 *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 11-12. Measure 11 features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. It continues with triplet patterns in both hands.

12 *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 12-13. Measure 12 features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. It continues with triplet patterns in both hands.

13 *p* *rit.*

Musical notation for measures 13-14. Measure 13 features a piano (*p*) dynamic. Measure 14 features a ritardando (*rit.*) dynamic. Both measures contain triplet patterns.

15 **Agitato** *p* *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 15-17. Measure 15 starts with the tempo marking **Agitato** and a piano (*p*) dynamic. It features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. The notation consists of continuous triplet patterns.

18 *dim.* *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 18-20. Measure 18 features a decrescendo (*dim.*) dynamic. Measure 19 features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. The notation consists of continuous triplet patterns.

21 *cresc.* *dim.*

Musical notation for measures 21-24. Measure 21 features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. Measure 22 features a decrescendo (*dim.*) dynamic. The notation consists of continuous triplet patterns.

25 *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 25-27. Measure 25 features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. The notation consists of continuous triplet patterns.

28 *mp* *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 28-30. Measure 28 features a mezzo-piano (*mp*) dynamic. Measure 29 features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. The notation consists of continuous triplet patterns.

31 *dim.* *mp* *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 31-33. Measure 31 features a decrescendo (*dim.*) dynamic. Measure 32 features a mezzo-piano (*mp*) dynamic. Measure 33 features a crescendo (*cresc.*) dynamic. The notation consists of continuous triplet patterns.

34

37

40

43

Lento ♩ = 54
46

48

49

50

51 *V*
cresc.

52 *V*
cresc.

53 *f*
dim.

54 *dim.*

55 *V*
dim.

56 *liberamente*
mp *dim.* *3*

60 *3* *rit. molto* *pp*

Fra Martino e compagnia bella

(per clarinettisti in erba)

Diego Casadei

♩ = 60

Clarinet in B $\flat$

6

12

17

22

27

32

37

41

Passacaglia in Si b minore

Diego Casadei
16 Apr 2016

33

37

41

45

47

49

53

56

This page of the musical score for 'Passacaglia in Si b minore' contains seven staves of music, numbered 33 through 56. The music is written in a single melodic line on a treble clef staff with a key signature of two flats (B-flat and E-flat). The notation includes various rhythmic values such as eighth, sixteenth, and thirty-second notes, as well as rests and accidentals. Slurs and ties are used to indicate phrasing and melodic continuity. The piece concludes with a double bar line at measure 56.

Passacaglia in Si b minore

Diego Casadei

16 Apr 2016

Clarinet in B $\flat$

Trombone

Measures 1-4 of the Clarinet in B $\flat$ and Trombone parts. The Clarinet part features a melodic line with eighth-note patterns and slurs. The Trombone part provides a harmonic accompaniment with dotted rhythms and slurs.

B $\flat$ Cl.

Tbn.

Measures 4-8 of the B $\flat$ Cl. and Tbn. parts. The B $\flat$ Cl. part continues the melodic line with eighth-note patterns. The Tbn. part continues the harmonic accompaniment with dotted rhythms.

B $\flat$ Cl.

Tbn.

Measures 8-12 of the B $\flat$ Cl. and Tbn. parts. The B $\flat$ Cl. part features a more complex melodic line with slurs. The Tbn. part continues the harmonic accompaniment with dotted rhythms.

B $\flat$ Cl.

Tbn.

Measures 12-16 of the B $\flat$ Cl. and Tbn. parts. The B $\flat$ Cl. part continues the melodic line with eighth-note patterns. The Tbn. part continues the harmonic accompaniment with dotted rhythms.

B $\flat$ Cl.

Tbn.

Measures 16-20 of the B $\flat$ Cl. and Tbn. parts. The B $\flat$ Cl. part continues the melodic line with eighth-note patterns. The Tbn. part continues the harmonic accompaniment with dotted rhythms.

Passacaglia in Si b minore

20

B♭ Cl.

Musical staff for B♭ Clarinet, measures 20-24. The staff contains a melodic line with dotted rhythms and slurs.

Tbn.

Musical staff for Trombone, measures 20-24. The staff contains a rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes and slurs.

25

B♭ Cl.

Musical staff for B♭ Clarinet, measures 25-27. The staff contains a melodic line with slurs and accents.

Tbn.

Musical staff for Trombone, measures 25-27. The staff contains a rhythmic accompaniment with slurs.

28

B♭ Cl.

Musical staff for B♭ Clarinet, measures 28-30. The staff contains a melodic line with slurs and accents.

Tbn.

Musical staff for Trombone, measures 28-30. The staff contains a rhythmic accompaniment with slurs.

31

B♭ Cl.

Musical staff for B♭ Clarinet, measures 31-33. The staff contains a melodic line with slurs and accents.

Tbn.

Musical staff for Trombone, measures 31-33. The staff contains a rhythmic accompaniment with slurs.

34

B♭ Cl.

Musical staff for B♭ Clarinet, measures 34-37. The staff contains a melodic line with slurs and accents.

Tbn.

Musical staff for Trombone, measures 34-37. The staff contains a rhythmic accompaniment with slurs.

38

B♭ Cl.

Musical staff for B♭ Clarinet, measures 38-41. The staff contains a melodic line with slurs and accents.

Tbn.

Musical staff for Trombone, measures 38-41. The staff contains a rhythmic accompaniment with slurs.

Passacaglia in Si b minore

41
B♭ Cl.

41
Tbn.

44
B♭ Cl.

44
Tbn.

47
B♭ Cl.

47
Tbn.

50
B♭ Cl.

50
Tbn.

53
B♭ Cl.

53
Tbn.

56
B♭ Cl.

56
Tbn.

Happy birthday

Diego Casadei (31.12.2020)

♩ = 100

Clarinet in B $\flat$

Musical notation for Clarinet in B $\flat$, measures 1-5. The piece is in 3/4 time with a key signature of one sharp (F#). The notation includes quarter notes, eighth notes, and triplet eighth notes. There are three triplet markings over eighth notes in measures 1, 3, and 5.

B $\flat$ Cl.

Musical notation for B $\flat$ Cl., measures 6-10. The notation includes quarter notes, eighth notes, and triplet eighth notes. There are three triplet markings over eighth notes in measures 6, 8, and 10. Accents (>) are placed over eighth notes in measures 7, 9, and 10.

B $\flat$ Cl.

Musical notation for B $\flat$ Cl., measures 11-15. The notation includes quarter notes, eighth notes, and triplet eighth notes. There are three triplet markings over eighth notes in measures 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15. An accent (>) is placed over the first eighth note in measure 11. The piece ends with a double bar line and repeat dots.

Tante, tante scale

Eeguire con diverse articolazioni.
Se possibile, estendere ai sovracuti.

Diego Casadei

The musical score consists of ten staves of music, each representing a different scale. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 2/4. The scales are:

- Minore naturale (Measures 1-5)
- Minore armonica (Measures 6-10)
- Minore melodica (Measures 11-15)
- Maggiore (Measures 16-20)
- Esatonale (Measures 21-24)
- Ottatonica (Measures 25-28)
- Pentatonica (Measures 29-32)
- Cromatica (Measures 33-36)
- (Measures 37-38)
- (Measures 39-42)

Measures are numbered at the beginning of each staff: 6, 11, 16, 21, 25, 29, 31, 34, 39. Triplet markings (3) are present in several measures, and some notes are marked with an 'x'.

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240

Musical staff 240: Treble clef, key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets and some notes marked with an 'x'.

245

Musical staff 245: Treble clef, key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets and some notes marked with an 'x'.

249

Musical staff 249: Treble clef, key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets and some notes marked with an 'x'.

253

Musical staff 253: Treble clef, key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets and some notes marked with an 'x'.

255

Musical staff 255: Treble clef, key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets and some notes marked with an 'x'.

258

Musical staff 258: Treble clef, key signature of two flats (Bb, Eb). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets.

263

Musical staff 263: Treble clef, key signature of two flats (Bb, Eb). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets.

268

Musical staff 268: Treble clef, key signature of two flats (Bb, Eb). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets.

273

Musical staff 273: Treble clef, key signature of two flats (Bb, Eb). The staff contains a sequence of eighth notes with triplets and some notes marked with an 'x'.

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